

BONE TISSUE SCAFFOLD BASED ON SHAPE MEMORY POLYMER

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ABSTRACT

Shape memory polymer (SMP) is a kind of smart materials, which can retain a temporary shape and recover the initial shape under some external stimuli. Duo to its biodegradability, easy forming properties and shape memory effect, SMP has been widely used in bio-medical applications. This paper details an application of SMP on porous bone tissue scaffold. Compared with traditional bone tissue scaffold, the scaffold based on SMP possesses advantages of low cost, easy assembly and easy adjustment. And most importantly, the adaptable bone tissue scaffold will adapt to keep the best fixed state. Besides, design of bone tissue scaffold is based on the biological structure, which high porosity and high specific surface area of these nature-inspired scaffolds will promote the growth of new bone tissue. Combining with 4D printing, it can realize customization. Bone tissue scaffold based on SMP exhibit excellent performance and proved to be a potential application in traditional bone tissue scaffold.

Design of bone tissue scaffold

(a) natural lotus root structure with plural holes, 3D images of lotus root-like biomimetic scaffold with (b)circular holes LRL-I (c) polygonal pores LRL-II

(a) natural bone tissue structure, 3D images of co-continuous cellular-like biomimetic scaffold with (b)random non-direction holes CCC-1 (c) random orientation holes CCC-2

Fabrication and characterization

Micro-CT examinations of LRL-1 (50% porosity), LRL-2 (50% porosity), CCC-1 (60% porosity) and CCC-2 (60% porosity)

Nature-inspired porous bone tissue scaffolds fabricated by 4D printing

Functional verification

Illustration of the shape recovery procedure by FEA and experiment